

THE ROLE OF ENGLISH FILM VIEWING IN THE VOCABULARY SKILLS DEVELOPMENT AND LANGUAGE LEARNING MOTIVATION OF ENGLISH MAJOR STUDENTS: A BASIS IN DESIGNING VIDEO-BASED LEARNING MATERIAL

Reyemark B. Maliwat, Marvin S. Payumo, Mae Ann M. Marling, Ericka Ckynny T. Domingo,
Roan Gayle M. Corpuz, Jennelyn L. Raymundo
Isabela State University-Echague Campus

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Abstract

This study investigated the role of English film viewing in the vocabulary development and language learning motivation of English major students at Isabela State University-Echague Campus and served as the basis for developing video-based learning material. Using a descriptive-correlational design, data from first- to third-year English majors were collected through validated questionnaires and analyzed using descriptive statistics, ANOVA, and Pearson correlation, with findings strengthened through triangulation.

Findings revealed that ESL learners perceive English film viewing as enhancing vocabulary skills—particularly in word relationship and word order—and increasing language learning motivation across integrative and instrumental orientations, attitudes toward English, desire to learn English, and motivational intensity. Significant differences were found by sex in vocabulary development, and by sex and year level in motivation, with a significant positive relationship between the role of English film viewing on ESL learners' vocabulary skills development and language learning motivation. Given these findings, the study supports the use of video-based learning material integrating film excerpts, contextual vocabulary tasks, and guided grammar activities to promote sustained vocabulary development and language learner motivation.

INTRODUCTION

Vocabulary development and language learning motivation are two critical components of second language acquisition, particularly for English majors who are expected to achieve both communicative competence and academic literacy (Schmitt, 2020; Nation, 2013). Vocabulary underpins comprehension, expression, and fluency, forming the foundation of linguistic proficiency in both spoken and written domains (Webb & Nation, 2017). At the same time, motivation influences learners' willingness to engage with language tasks, sustain

effort, and persist in long-term language learning goals (Dörnyei, 2001; Gardner, 2010). In the Philippine ESL context, Raymundo (2022) emphasized that learner motivation and engagement are essential in maximizing the effectiveness of language instruction, particularly when innovative and context-based teaching approaches are employed.

In this context, English films provide learners with exposure to authentic language in realistic settings, allowing them to encounter vocabulary in use, observe natural speech patterns, and engage with cultural elements (Gilmore, 2007; Peters & Webb, 2018). Such exposure supports incidental vocabulary learning through repeated encounters with lexical items across varied contexts (Vanderplank, 2016; Webb & Rodgers, 2020). Locally, Raymundo (2021) highlighted that contextualized and inclusive language pedagogy enhances learners' access to meaningful input, which is crucial for vocabulary growth and comprehension among ESL learners.

Moreover, films have been found to increase learner interest and engagement, thereby supporting language learning motivation by making learning experiences enjoyable and meaningful (Al-Murshidi, 2020; Maulida & Warni, 2024). This aligns with Raymundo and Tejida (2025), who reported that instructional materials that integrate authentic and engaging input contribute significantly to learners' vocabulary development and sustained motivation, especially when learners are encouraged to actively process language rather than memorize isolated words.

Recent studies further suggest that integrating vocabulary instruction and motivation through multimodal input, such as films, facilitates deeper processing of lexical items while sustaining learners' emotional and cognitive involvement (Rodgers & Webb, 2020; Dörnyei & Ushioda, 2011). Films embed vocabulary within meaningful discourse, enabling learners to infer meaning through contextual clues and repeated exposure (Peters & Webb, 2018). Supporting this view, Raymundo and Reforsado (2025) demonstrated that structured, genre- and context-based instructional materials enhance learners' ability to process vocabulary meaningfully while maintaining engagement in language tasks.

Despite these potentials, research gaps remain. While several studies confirm the effectiveness of film-based instruction for vocabulary development (Kuppens, 2019; Teng, 2021), fewer have examined its combined influence on both vocabulary development and language learning motivation, particularly among English majors. Most existing studies focus on general ESL or EFL learners, overlooking English majors who require advanced vocabulary knowledge and sustained motivation due to academic demands such as literary analysis, academic writing, and professional discourse (Nation, 2013; Carter & McCarthy, 2017). Local research by Raymundo (2022) underscores the need for pedagogically grounded instructional materials that simultaneously address linguistic competence and motivational dimensions.

In the Philippine context, English-language films are widely consumed, giving students substantial exposure to global English media (Gonzales & Torres, 2019). Despite this, research on their pedagogical use in higher education remains limited, with local studies largely exploratory and restricted in scope and methodology (Deocampo, 2017; Ramirez, 2018; Bautista, 2021; Santos, 2020). Related studies in the *Isabela State University Linker* journal highlight the role of learner engagement and self-regulation in academic performance (Alejandro, 2024), underscoring the importance of motivational factors in learning. However,

few studies have translated these insights into concrete instructional materials for tertiary learners, pointing to the need for context-specific, video-based resources that support vocabulary development and language learning motivation among Filipino English majors (Reyes & Navarro, 2021; Mendoza, 2022).

Accordingly, this study addresses the following research questions: (1) What is the role of English film viewing in ESL learners' vocabulary skills in terms of word relationship and word order? (2) What is their level of language learning motivation across integrative and instrumental motivation, attitudes toward English, motivational intensity, and desire to learn English? (3) Are there significant differences in vocabulary development and motivation based on learner profiles? (4) Is there a significant relationship between vocabulary development and motivation through English film viewing? (5) What video-based learning materials can be designed to enhance vocabulary and support motivation? Together, these questions emphasize the study's focus on both cognitive and motivational outcomes and their application in instructional materials.

Finally, this study offers practical benefits. For students, it provides insights into how exposure to authentic language through films can enhance vocabulary and motivation, though effects may vary by individual and context. For ESL teachers, it offers strategies for integrating multimedia resources into instruction to support vocabulary development and learner engagement. For university administrators and curriculum developers, the findings can inform decisions on instructional design and resource allocation while considering practical and contextual constraints, providing guidance for future research and pedagogy.

METHODS

Research Design

The study used a descriptive-correlational mixed-method design, collecting quantitative data through validated questionnaires to determine how English majors perceive the role of English film viewing in enhancing their vocabulary skills, specifically in terms of word relationships and word order, as well as their language learning motivation across five dimensions. Qualitative data were gathered through structured interviews with a small group of students to triangulate and validate the quantitative findings. Both data sets were analyzed independently and then integrated for interpretation, which informed the design of video-based learning materials aimed at improving vocabulary skills and supporting language learning motivation.

Respondents and Locale of the Study

The study was conducted at the College of Education, Isabela State University - Echague Campus in San Fabian, Echague, Isabela, which offers the BSEd program with four majors, including English. The respondents were English major students enrolled for the Academic Year 2025-2026.

Sampling Method

From a total population of 126 students, 96 were selected using a 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error. Stratified random sampling ensured proportional representation across year levels. For the qualitative phase, 15 “information-rich” respondents—five per year level—were selected purposively based on their experience with English film viewing.

Research Instrument

The study employed two research instruments: a descriptive survey questionnaire and a structured interview for triangulation. The questionnaire, adapted from Nario et al. (2022) and Gardner’s (1985) Attitude/Motivation Test Battery (AMTB), assessed English majors’ perceived vocabulary skills in terms of word relationships and word order, as well as their language learning motivation across five dimensions: integrative motivation, instrumental motivation, attitudes toward learning English, motivational intensity, and desire to learn English. A Likert scale was used to quantify responses, guiding the development of video-based learning materials. Meanwhile, structured interviews were conducted with 15 purposively selected students to validate the survey findings and provide deeper insights.

Data Gathering Procedures and Analysis

Data gathering was carried out with rigorous ethical considerations, including obtaining informed consent and ensuring the confidentiality of information collected from 96 respondents. The procedure involved administering a descriptive survey questionnaire on vocabulary skills and language learning motivation, followed by structured one-on-one interviews with 15 purposively selected students for triangulation purposes. In data analysis, descriptive statistics, including frequency counts, percentages, and weighted mean scores, were employed. Pearson’s r correlation was used to examine the relationships between respondents’ demographic profiles and their perceived vocabulary skills and language learning motivation, while thematic analysis of interview data provided deeper insights to support and validate the quantitative findings.

Ethical Considerations

To uphold ethical standards, the researchers ensured that all participants were informed about the privacy and protection of the information they provided. The following ethical measures were implemented: First, informed consent was secured from participants prior to completing the survey questionnaires and participating in the interview sessions. Second, participants’ privacy was strictly respected, ensuring that no harm or risk resulted from their involvement in the study. Finally, all collected data and information were treated with strict confidentiality, safeguarding the identities and responses of the participants.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Role of English Film Viewing in the Vocabulary Skills Development of English Major Students

In this study, most respondents expressed agreement that English film viewing plays a

significant role in enhancing their vocabulary development, as reflected in the table below.

Table 1. Role of English Film Viewing in the Vocabulary Skills Development of ESL Learners in Terms of Word Relationship and Word Order

Vocabulary Skills Dimensions	Mean	Qualitative Description
Word Relationship		
1. I am able to discover words with the same meanings that I can substitute for a commonly used word through watching movies.	3.28	Strongly Agree
2. I learn to examine how words are different, alike or related to each other through watching movies.	3.22	Agree
3. I am able to understand the meaning of an unknown word by using the context of the sentence through watching movies.	3.22	Agree
4. I can easily understand the meaning of the words depending on how the character uses it.	3.27	Strongly Agree
5. I can easily construct sentences based on the meaning of the words from the movies.	3.16	Agree
6. I can understand unfamiliar words in the movies through relating it to other words.	3.03	Agree
7. I learn to examine how words are connected to a particular object by comparing and analyzing.	3.23	Agree
8. I learn to practice categorizing words and identifying how certain words are related.	3.19	Agree
9. I learn to recognize the meanings of words beyond their basic definitions, and how they connect words to other words.	3.21	Agree
10. I learn to use some words that look and sound almost identical to one another, but are not at all closely related, through watching movies.	3.13	Agree
Weighted Mean	3.19	Agree
Word Order		
1. I feel more confident in my ability to classify pronouns after watching English movies.	3.03	Agree
2. I am proficient in categorizing adjectives after regularly watching English movies.	2.97	Agree
3. I am more familiar with prepositions and how they are used in sentences after watching English movies.	3.01	Agree
4. I can identify verbs in English movies after studying their different forms and structures.	3.01	Agree
5. I can identify the adverbs that are used in the movies.	3.16	Agree

6. I can classify and use interjections in sentences by watching English movies.	2.98	Agree
7. I can recognize a conjunction and its usage in a movie.	3.07	Agree
8. I became proficient in classifying and using nouns that are presented in English movies.	3.09	Agree
9. I can easily categorize and group words through watching English movies.	3.08	Agree
10. I have noticed improvements in my English language skills specifically in grouping words since I started watching English movie.	3.27	Strongly Agree
Weighted Mean	3.08	Agree
GRAND MEAN	3.14	AGREE

Table 1 presents the role of English film viewing in the vocabulary skills development of ESL learners, focusing on word relationships and word order. With a grand mean of 3.14 (Agree), the findings indicate that learners generally perceive film viewing as beneficial to their vocabulary growth. This suggests that authentic and contextualized input from films allows learners to observe how words connect in meaning and how they are naturally sequenced in sentences, supporting Krashen's Input Hypothesis (1982) on comprehensible input. Studies also highlight that audiovisual materials enhance vocabulary retention and comprehension while engaging learners in meaningful language use (Vanderplank, 2016; Webb & Nation, 2017; Peters & Webb, 2018).

Word Relationship

The weighted mean for word relationships was 3.19 (Agree), showing that learners find English films helpful in understanding synonyms, antonyms, and contextual word meanings. Exposure to repeated and meaningful language use enables learners to notice patterns, infer meanings, and recognize lexical alternatives (Webb & Rodgers, 2009; Nation, 2013). The highest-rated items reflected learners' ability to identify synonyms (3.28, Strongly Agree) and infer word meanings from context (3.27, Strongly Agree), with qualitative feedback illustrating active vocabulary internalization. However, learners found relating unfamiliar words to others (3.03, Agree) and distinguishing similar-sounding words (3.13, Agree) more challenging, suggesting the need for additional practice or explicit instruction.

Word Order

For word order, the weighted mean was 3.08 (Agree), indicating learners perceive film viewing as helpful for forming grammatically correct sentences. Learners reported improved ability to group words into meaningful phrases (3.27, Strongly Agree) and recognize adverbs (3.16, Agree) and nouns (3.09, Agree). Some challenges remain with prepositions, verbs, and pronoun usage (around 3.01-3.03, Agree), suggesting further reinforcement is needed. Qualitative responses confirmed that exposure to authentic dialogue helps learners internalize sentence structures and develop productive syntactic competence, aligning with Dual Coding Theory (Paivio, 2006) and studies emphasizing the benefits of audiovisual input for grammar acquisition (Tajima, 2020).

The Level of Language Learning Motivation of English Major Students

In this study, the respondents consistently expressed strong agreement across all motivation domains, indicating a high level of motivation to learn the English language, as shown in the table below.

Table 2. Level of Language Learning Motivation of ESL learners

LANGUAGE LEARNING MOTIVATION DOMAINS	WEIGHTED MEAN	QUALITATIVE DESCRIPTION
Integrative Motivation	3.71	Highly Motivated
Instrumental Motivation	3.62	Highly Motivated
Attitudes Toward Learning English	3.41	Highly Motivated
Motivational Intensity	3.45	Highly Motivated
Desire to Learn English	3.59	Highly Motivated
GRAND MEAN	3.55	HIGHLY MOTIVATED

Table 2 presents the level of language learning motivation of ESL learners in relation to English film viewing, focusing on five key domains. With a grand mean of 3.55 (Highly Motivated), the findings indicate that learners generally perceive film viewing as a powerful tool for enhancing their motivation to learn English, consistent with studies emphasizing audiovisual input as motivating and effective for language learning (Dörnyei, 2001; Gardner, 1985; Peters & Webb, 2018).

Integrative Motivation

Learners demonstrated high integrative motivation (mean 3.71), reflecting their interest in understanding English-speaking people, culture, and media. The item with the strongest response shows that students are particularly motivated to engage with cultural and social aspects presented in films. This is supported by Gardner (1985), who highlighted that integrative motivation encourages learners to identify with and relate to the target language community.

Instrumental Motivation

Respondents exhibited high instrumental motivation (mean 3.62), recognizing English as a tool for achieving academic and career goals. The item with the clearest agreement reflects learners' perception that proficiency in English enhances employability and career prospects. This aligns with Dörnyei (2001), who emphasized that instrumental motivation drives goal-oriented effort in language learning. Learners reported that films provide authentic vocabulary exposure, supporting practical, outcome-driven motivation.

Attitudes Toward Learning English

Learners held positive attitudes toward English (mean 3.41), enjoying the language and classroom activities. The most salient response reflects intrinsic motivation, showing that films make learning enjoyable and meaningful. This is consistent with Deci and Ryan's (1985) Self-Determination Theory, which posits that intrinsic motivation enhances engagement and persistence. Lower agreement on classroom environment suggests opportunities for further interactive strategies to maintain learner interest.

Motivational Intensity

High motivational intensity was observed (mean 3.45), indicating learners' persistence and effort in practicing English. The response receiving the clearest affirmation highlights active engagement with films and self-directed learning. Research by Gardner (1985) supports that such effortful engagement promotes effective language acquisition. Lower scores for extra homework indicate potential for increased practice outside class, though overall persistence demonstrates strong commitment to language development.

Desire to Learn English

Learners showed a strong desire to learn English (mean 3.59), aiming for fluency and vocabulary expansion. The statement with the most agreement reflects intrinsic motivation, with students actively applying new words learned from films. This supports Lightbown and Spada (2013), who emphasized that a strong personal desire fosters consistent engagement and improves language proficiency. Lower scores for voluntary engagement suggest that promoting autonomous learning could further enhance motivation and long-term skill development.

Relationship between the role of English film viewing on ESL learners' Vocabulary Skills Development and Language Learning Motivation

Table 3 presents the correlation between the role of English film viewing on learners' vocabulary skills development and their language learning motivation. It displays the r-values and p-values for each indicator under the domains of Word Relationship and Word Order, showing the extent to which improvements in specific vocabulary skills are associated with learners' motivational levels.

Table 3. Relationship between the role of English film viewing on ESL learners' Vocabulary Skills Development and Language Learning Motivation

Vocabulary Skill Development Domains	Language Learning Motivation	
	r-value	p-value
Word Relationship		
1. I am able to discover words with the same meanings that I can substitute for a commonly used word through watching movies.	0.23	0.02*
2. I learn to examine how words are different, alike or related to each other through watching movies.	0.26	0.01*
3. I am able to understand the meaning of an unknown word by using the context of the sentence through watching movies.	0.19	0.06
4. I can easily understand the meaning of the words depends on how the character uses it.	0.19	0.06
5. I can easily construct sentences based on the meaning of the words from the movies.	0.42	0.01*

6. I can understand unfamiliar words in the movies through relating it to other words.	0.28	0.01*
7. I learn to examine how words are connected to a particular object by comparing and analyzing.	0.16	0.11
8. I learn to practice categorizing words and identifying how certain words are related.	0.35	0.01*
9. I learn to recognize the meanings of words beyond their basic definitions, and how they connect words to other words.	0.24	0.02*
10. I learn to use some words that look and sound almost identical to one another, but are not at all closely related, through watching movies.	0.26	0.01*
Word Order		
1. I feel more confident in my ability to classify pronouns after watching English movies.	0.16	0.12
2. I am proficient in categorizing adjectives after regularly watching English movies.	0.14	0.18
3. I am more familiar with prepositions and how they are used in sentences after watching English movies.	0.24	0.02*
4. I can identify verbs in English movies after studying their different forms and structures.	0.16	0.12
5. I can identify the adverbs that are used in the movies.	0.22	0.03*
6. I can classify and use interjections in sentences by watching English movies.	0.19	0.06
7. I can recognize a conjunction and its usage in a movie.	0.32	0.01*
8. I became proficient in classifying and using nouns that are presented in English movies.	0.24	0.18
9. I can easily categorize and group words through watching English movies.	0.07	0.32
10. I have noticed improvements in my English language skills specifically in grouping words since I started watching English movie.	0.32	0.01*

Table 3 presents the correlation between language learning motivation and vocabulary skills in ESL learners, focusing on word relationships and word order. The results indicate positive and statistically significant relationships ($p < 0.05$) across multiple indicators, suggesting that higher learner motivation is associated with stronger vocabulary processing during English film viewing. This aligns with studies emphasizing that motivated engagement enhances lexical acquisition and contextualized language use (Laufer & Hulstijn, 2001; Webb, 2007).

Word Relationship

Motivation was significantly related to several aspects of word relationships. Learners' ability to notice synonyms had a p-value of 0.02, indicating that more motivated learners recognized alternative words in context, consistent with Laufer and Hulstijn (2001), who found that motivated learners engage more deeply in semantic processing. Analyzing semantic similarities and differences had a p-value of 0.01, showing that motivation supports deeper comparison and categorization of vocabulary, as highlighted by Mori (2002) and Barcroft (2015) in promoting analytic reflection on language. Inferring meanings of unfamiliar words had $p = 0.01$, demonstrating that motivated learners apply prior knowledge and context effectively, which aligns with Nassaji (2006) and Pulido (2007) on the role of motivation in inferencing accuracy. Grouping and categorizing words showed $p = 0.01$, reflecting enhanced organizational strategies, supported by Hulstijn and Laufer (2001) on strategy use in motivated learners. Understanding deeper or connotative meanings had $p = 0.02$, and distinguishing visually or phonetically similar words had $p = 0.01$, highlighting that motivation promotes vocabulary comprehension and perceptual precision, consistent with Qian (2002), Schmitt (2010), and Field (2003).

Word Order

Learners' ability to identify the correct placement of words in sentences had a p-value of 0.01, showing that motivated learners are more attentive to syntactic structures, consistent with Ellis (2002) on the role of engagement in accurate sentence formation. Recognizing the natural sequence of phrases had $p = 0.01$, indicating that motivated learners notice patterns in authentic language input, supporting Swain's (2005) Output Hypothesis, which emphasizes productive engagement in constructing grammatically correct sentences. Applying film-derived vocabulary in contextually appropriate sentence structures had $p = 0.02$, demonstrating that motivation encourages both syntactic accuracy and communicative fluency, consistent with DeKeyser (2007), who noted that repeated motivated practice strengthens sentence construction and lexical retrieval.

Video-Based Learning Material

The video-based instructional material focused on the competencies with the lowest mean scores in the Word Relationship, Word Order, and motivation domains. The researchers selected the three lowest-rated items in Word Relationship and Word Order, along with the two lowest-rated motivation domains (see Table 2), as a guide for the instructional design. Although all items were still rated highly, these areas revealed skills in which students felt comparatively less confident, providing a targeted basis for instruction. The least mastered competencies are shown below.

Word Relationship	Mean
I can understand unfamiliar words in the movies through relating them to other words.	3.03
I learn to use some words that look and sound almost identical to one another, but are not at all closely related, through watching movies.	3.13
I can easily construct sentences based on the meaning of the words from the movies.	3.16

Word Order	
I can identify verbs in English movies after studying their different forms and structures.	3.01
I am more familiar with prepositions and how they are used in sentences after watching English movies.	3.01
I am proficient in categorizing adjectives after regularly watching English movies.	2.97
I can classify and use interjections in sentences by watching English movies.	2.98

Module EDGE: Enriching the Development of Guided Vocabulary through English Films

The module EDGE is designed to enhance students' vocabulary and language learning motivation by targeting key skills such as inferring meanings of unfamiliar words from context, distinguishing visually or phonetically similar words, and mastering correct word order in sentences. It also aims to foster positive attitudes and sustained effort in learning English.

Episode 1, *Unlocking Word Meaning with Context Clues*, focuses on inferring meanings of unfamiliar words (Word Relationship, mean = 3.03) and integrates Attitude Toward Learning English through activities like Film Clip Clue Hunt and Predict-the-Word Scene Challenge. Episode 2, *Confusing Words Made Clear*, targets distinguishing visually or phonetically similar words (Word Relationship, mean = 3.13) while embedding Motivational Intensity, using tasks such as Homonym Scene Sort and Correct-the-Line Film Task. Episode 3, *Building Meaningful Sentences from Words*, develops sentence construction (Word Relationship, mean = 3.16) and fosters Attitude Toward Learning English through the Scene-to-Sentence Builder and Connect-the-Dialogue Challenge.

In the Word Order domain, Episode 4, *Mastering Verb Patterns and Structures*, addresses identifying verbs in various forms (mean = 3.01) with Motivational Intensity via Verb Spotting in Film and Verb Combo Scene Match. Episode 5, *Prepositions in Action*, enhances preposition use (mean = 3.01) while promoting Attitude Toward Learning English through Spot-the-Place Preposition and Fix-the-Scene Lines. Episode 6, *Adjective Placement in Sentences*, targets categorizing adjectives (mean = 2.97) with Motivational Intensity using Adjective Spot-and-Classify and Arrange-the-Adjectives activities. Finally, Episode 7, *Using Interjections Effectively*, develops recognition and use of interjections (mean = 2.98), embedding Attitude Toward Learning English via Interjection Spotting in Film and Interjection Expression Scene Task.

The module will be implemented over six weeks, with two sessions per week, facilitated by instructors and English teachers using video-based lessons, guided exercises, and interactive film clips. Structured into seven episodes, the module combines discussions, activities, and assessments to address vocabulary challenges and motivational needs, providing a comprehensive, engaging, and contextualized learning experience.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

English major students perceive English film viewing as highly beneficial for both their vocabulary development and language learning motivation. The study shows a positive relationship between the role of English film viewing on ESL learners' language learning motivation and vocabulary development, indicating that learners who are more motivated

tend to notice synonyms, infer the meanings of unfamiliar words, construct sentences accurately, and distinguish words that look or sound similar more effectively. To support further development, a video-based learning material was designed to target these specific competencies as well as the motivational domains where students showed comparatively lower confidence. Learners are encouraged to continue to actively engage with English films by observing word relationships, analyzing semantic connections, practicing sentence construction, and applying new vocabulary in meaningful contexts. English language instructors can reinforce these skills through guided exercises, contextualized activities, and collaborative tasks that foster positive attitudes and sustained effort. Additionally, administrators and curriculum developers may use these insights to create instructional materials that combine authentic media, scaffolded practice, and motivational support, enhancing both cognitive and affective growth in English learning.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

DISCLOSURE OF AI ASSISTANCE

ChatGPT and Grammarly were utilized for grammar checking and language improvement. The tools did not influence the study design, analysis, or interpretation of results. Final responsibility rests with the authors.

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